

OPTIMIZED CURE CYCLE TO MINIMIZE FIBER STRESSES IN POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: A technique for the cure cycle optimization for a thermoset polymer matrix composites is developed. In this technique, a given polymer is cured around a pretensioned fiber. As the curing continues, the volume of polymer changes due to its thermal expansion and polymerization shrinkage. The matrix volume change occurring after the point in the cure cycle when fiber-matrix interface has developed enough shear strength affects the fiber tension. An automated feedback system is developed to change the heating rate proportional to the change in fiber tension so as to produce the minimum fiber tension change. Such a cure cycle is defined as the optimum. The volumetric dilatometer is also used to independently monitor the matrix volume change during the standard and the optimum cure cycles. The comparison between the two techniques show that the cure cycle that produces minimum change in fiber tension also produces minimum change in polymer volume.

KEYWORDS: cure cycle, cure shrinkage, thermal expansion, residual stresses, polymerization

INTRODUCTION

Several studies have been conducted to understand the cure kinetics of thermoset resins [1,2]. One of the main objectives of these studies has been to understand how the chemical and thermal changes encountered during curing of these resins lead to the residual stresses in composites [3,4]. The effect of residual stresses generated during curing is reflected in the mechanical properties of cured composites [5]. In calculating the thermal residual stress in composites, a stress-free state at the highest temperature in the curing cycle is commonly assumed. Thus the attention is focused on the optimization of the cooling path so as to minimize the residual stresses in composites. However, before the cooldown begins, the matrix undergoes significant volume changes [6,7]. These volume changes also produce residual stress in composites. This residual stress is then relieved by several mechanisms such as fiber waviness, warping, delamination, and microcracking. The volume change during the cure of a conventional polymer resin is displayed in Figure 1 [7]. Cure shrinkage of the thermosets can be divided into polymerization and thermal shrinkage. Thermal expansion is seen in region 1 as the polymer is heated. Polymerization shrinkage (region 2) occurs during crosslinking and depends on the chemical composition and polymerization reaction (i.e. addition versus condensation reactions) [8]. A polymer is more dense than its monomer, and the resulting shrinkage upon polymerization can reach 10 to 20% [9]. In region 3, the system

has equilibrated after the completion of polymerization. In region 4, thermal contraction is seen as the polymer cools.

The technique used in this study relies on utilizing the fiber tension change when a polymer is cured around the fiber to determine the optimum cure cycle. A typical result of fiber tension change during the standard cure cycle for a carbon/ epoxy composite is shown in Figure 2 [10]. When the temperature is increased from the first dwell to the second dwell period, the fiber tension drops because of matrix thermal expansion. During the second dwell period the fiber tension begins to increase because of matrix shrinkage produced by its crosslinking. Then, the fiber tension remains unchanged suggesting that the system has reached equilibrium and the matrix polymerization is complete. Finally, during the cooldown the matrix thermal shrinkage produces an increase in fiber tension. The fiber tension change profile (Figure 2) correlate quite well with the matrix volume change curve (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Volume change during cure of a conventional polyester resin (data from ref. 7).

Figure 2: Change in fiber tension during the standard cure cycle of a single fiber gr/ep composite.

This paper presents a method to obtain an optimum cure cycle for a given fiber-matrix system. The optimum cure cycle has been considered to be the one which produces minimum change in fiber tension during the cure cycle. The results are independently verified by determining the matrix volume change using volumetric dilatometry.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Material

The materials used in this study were AS4 graphite fiber and 3501-6 epoxy resin, both obtained from Hercules.

Cure Cycle Optimization Procedure

The procedure involves applying a known tension to a fiber having fixed ends, and then monitoring the change in the fiber tension when the matrix around the fiber is subjected to a given temperature-time curing cycle. One end of the fiber is fixed to a rigid support. The other end of the fiber is passed through a cavity in a silicone mold and glued to a load cell. The thickness of the base and sides of the silicone mold were kept as small as possible (about 0.3 mm) to minimize the effect of silicone mold volume change on experimental results. A predetermined tension is applied to the fiber. The silicone cavity is filled with the degassed polymer and the cure cycle is applied by a strip-heater (see the top insert of Figure 2). The temperature is controlled by a computer. A ceramic plate is placed between the heated zone and the load cell to prevent heating of the load cell. The temperature is monitored by means of a thermocouple placed beside the specimen. The output from the load cell and the thermocouple is recorded during the entire curing process. A fiber pretension of 5 g was applied in all experiments.

A closed-loop feedback control system is developed which is based on the assumption that it is possible to find a cure cycle in which the polymer thermal expansion is simultaneously canceled by its cure shrinkage. The flow chart of the feedback system is shown in Figure 3. In this system, the polymer is heated to a temperature when the fiber tension begins to change. At this point, the polymer crosslinking has reached a state when the polymer volume changes affect the fiber tension. At this instant, the feedback system is turned on. The computer program automatically changes the heating rate once every minute proportional to the fiber tension change. An increase in fiber tension implies that the polymer is shrinking. Hence, the heating rate is increased to minimize the shrinkage with the thermal expansion. Similarly, when fiber tension decreases, the heating rate is decreased to allow cancellation of the thermal expansion part of polymer volume change with polymer cure shrinkage. The feedback system turns off the heat when there is no change in the fiber tension during a 30 min. temperature hold. The constant fiber tension implies that there is no polymer volume change hence the cure is complete.

Figure 3. The flow chart of the closed-loop feedback system for obtaining the optimum cure cycle for a given fiber-matrix system.

Volumetric Dilatometry

The volumetric dilatometer used was the GNOMIX, Inc. PVT Apparatus. This equipment has been described in detail in ref. [11]. Samples from 0.5 to 1.0 g of 3501-6 resin were used. Samples were cured using the same cure cycle as used in the fiber tension experiments. A constant pressure of 10 MPa was always maintained on the sample to prevent any evaporation of mercury, which boils at 357°C (675°F) at atmospheric pressure. The sample volume was recorded once every minute.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Standard Cure Cycle

The standard cure cycle for the 3501-6 epoxy resin consists of: heating the sample from room temperature to 116°C (240°F) in 30 minutes; hold the temperature at 116°C (240°F) for 60 minutes; raise the temperature from 116°C (240°F) to 177°C (350°F) in 25 minutes; hold the temperature at 177°C (350°F) for 240 minutes; cool the sample to room temperature in 60 minutes.

Figure 4 shows fiber force profile when the standard cure cycle is applied. During temperature increase from room to the first dwell at 116°C (240°F), the fiber force does not change significantly because the polymer is still able to freely flow around the fiber. As the heating starts again to raise the temperature to the second dwell at 177°C (350°F), a drop in the fiber tension is noticed. At this stage the matrix has polymerized to the point that matrix volume change can now affect the fiber tension. During this period both thermal expansion and crosslinking shrinkage of polymer occurs. However, the thermal expansion part of the matrix dominates over its crosslinking shrinkage because of the rapid heating rate. Hence, the net effect is a drop in the fiber load during this temperature increase. During the temperature hold at 177°C (350°F), the matrix thermal expansion stops, however, the volume shrinkage due to its crosslinking continues resulting in an increase in fiber force until it has reached a constant value. At this point, the resin cure is believed to be completed which results in an almost flat curve for the fiber force. During the cooldown, a decrease in matrix volume produces an increase in fiber load. The test was repeated three times using the same cure cycle and similar results were obtained.

Figure 4: Fiber tension profile during the standard cure cycle.

Figure 5 shows the volume change of the resin using the volumetric dilatometer during the standard cure cycle. The results correlate well with the proposed mechanisms that produced fiber load change (Figures 4 and 5). The only difference is that while the volumetric dilatometry can detect the matrix volume change at all instances of the cure cycle, the fiber tension experiment is able to respond to the matrix volume changes only after matrix polymerization has reached a critical point when fiber-matrix interface has developed enough shear strength. This critical point occurs towards the end of the first dwell period. That is why the matrix volume change detected by the volumetric dilatometer during the first temperature increase does not correspond with the fiber tension plot. However, during the

second temperature increase and the subsequent temperature hold, both techniques provide the same conclusion in regard to matrix volume change, that is, a net volume increase of matrix during the temperature increase from 116°C (240°F) to 177°C (350°F) followed by polymerization induced volume shrinkage during the temperature hold. Also, as the polymerization is completed (after about 4 hours), both fiber tension and volume change curves reach a plateau (Figures 4 and 5) until cooldown begins at which point the matrix volume begins to decrease.

Figure 5: Polymer volume change during the standard cure cycle.. A significant volume change occurs during the standard cure cycle.

Figure 6: Fiber tension profile during temperature hold period. The increase in fiber load is due to cure shrinkage of the matrix.

To further verify the proposed mechanism that produce change in fiber tension, another cure cycle was applied in which the first temperature hold at 116°C (240°F) was eliminated and the temperature was rapidly raised to the second dwell at 177°C (350°F), and then held constant, Figure 6. In such heating cycle since all the thermal expansion occurs when matrix is still able to flow around the fiber, it is believed that the only source of volume changes during the temperature hold that can be detected by the pretensioned fiber is the cure shrinkage. In such case, the fiber force is expected to increase with the degree of cure until the cure is completed

at which point there should be no change in the fiber force. Figure 6 shows the results obtained for this cure cycle which agree with the results expected with the proposed volume change mechanisms.

Optimum Cure Cycle

The matrix volume changes that occur during that standard cure cycle are undesirable as they produce curing induced fiber stresses which may cause fiber fracture [10] and fiber waviness [12]. The situation can be corrected by finding an optimum cycle that produces the minimum amount of matrix volume change. Using the fiber tension experiment, two approaches were adopted to find such a cure cycle, namely a trial-and-error approach and a feedback control system. These two methods and the results are described below.

Trial-And-Error Approach

A trial-and-error approach was first taken to find a cure cycle in which there is a simultaneous shrinkage due to cure and expansion due to thermal expansion of the same magnitude. For such a cure cycle the matrix volume and hence the fiber force will remain constant. Several different cure cycle experiments were conducted in which each cure cycle was modified based on the results obtained from the previous cure cycles. In all these cure cycles the curing was considered to be complete when there was no change in fiber tension during a 30 minute temperature hold period. The tests were continued until the cure cycle that produced the minimum matrix volume change was obtained. It usually took about four to five iterations to find an optimum cure cycle. Figure 7 shows the load and temperature profile for what is believed to be an optimum cure cycle for this particular type of resins. In this cycle the temperature is first increased linearly room temperature to 138°C (280°F) in 30 minutes and then again increased linearly to 177°C (350°F) in 210 minutes followed by a 30 minute hold at 177°C (350°F). It is believed that during the first 100 minutes of curing, the matrix is still able to freely flow around the fiber. As a result, any matrix volume change during this period is not detected by the fiber. After that time, matrix thermal expansion produced by the slow temperature increase is simultaneously canceled by its cure shrinkage which produces almost no net volume change and hence no fiber tension change.

Figure 7: The optimum cure cycle obtained using trial-and-error approach. The flat fiber tension curve indicates minimum matrix volume change.

The cure cycle obtained using the trial-and-error method was also used in volumetric dilatometry studies. The results are shown in Figure 8. It should be noted that the initial changes in polymer volume (during the first 100 minutes) do not affect the fiber force since the bond between the fiber and the resin is not fully developed yet. One more interesting observation that can be made from the comparison of the net matrix volume change in the standard and optimized cure cycles is that just prior to the start of cooldown the standard cure cycle produces larger net volume change (about 2%) compared to almost 0% net volume change in the optimum cure cycle (Figures 5 and 8). This may have important implication in the residual stresses developed in closed-mold processes.

Figure 8: Polymer volume change during the optimum cure cycle. The volume change profiles correlates well the fiber tension change during the same cure cycle (Figure 7).

Feed-back Control System

In another approach to finding an optimum cure cycle for a given fiber-matrix system, a computerized closed-loop feedback control system was developed. The details of the procedure are described in Experimental Method section.

Figure 9 shows results obtained using the feedback system for the same resin used in the trial-and-error approach. It can be seen that the fiber tension plot is almost completely flat. Also the heating rate is not linear as was used in the trial-and-error approach. The instantaneous correction in the heating rate to maintain a constant fiber tension allows the determination of an optimum cure cycle where there is almost complete cancellation of the matrix thermal expansion by its cure shrinkage.

Figure 9: The optimum cure cycle obtained using feedback control system. The flat fiber tension curve indicates minimum matrix volume change

Mechanical Properties

Some preliminary 3-point flexure experiments were also conducted on resin samples cured using the standard and optimum cure cycles. 3 specimens were tested for each case. The average flexural moduli of specimens cured using the standard the optimized cure cycles were 4.9 GPa, and 5.3 GPa, respectively. Considering the experimental scatter, these difference are not considered statistically significant. Hence, it was concluded that modifying the cure cycle did not change the polymer mechanical properties. Additional work on the effect of cure cycle on polymer glass transition temperature, and its strength and toughness is currently underway.

CONCLUSIONS

A new method is developed to understand mechanism of polymer resin cure in composite materials. The method is based on an observation that when a polymer matrix is cured around pretensioned fiber, it causes a change in fiber tension. The method was used to obtain a cure cycle that is considered to be optimum in the sense that it results in minimum change in the fiber stresses during cure. The fiber tension data is correlated with independent experiments on volumetric dilatometry. The volumetric dilatometer experiments show that there is a significant matrix volume change when a standard cure cycle is used. The optimized cure cycle results in minimum matrix volume change by allowing the matrix thermal expansion and cure shrinkage to occur simultaneously thus cancel each other out. Composite materials cured using such optimum cycles may have better dimensional stability and less likelihood of fiber failure, fiber waviness, etc. The developed procedure can also be used to detect the completeness of the resin cure which may result in a shorter cure cycle.

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